

NPE 1986 and NEP 2020 on Inclusive Education in India a Comparative Study

Umasankar Mandal

Teacher, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar College, Nadia, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Education is a systematic process of acquiring knowledge and a continuous practice of developing one's full potential. Through the process of education, it helps to reveal the full development of a person's inherent qualities. At the same time, one acquires the necessary skills to become a contributing member of the society. After India's independence, the National Commission for Education was established in 1986 for the overall development of the country and society. The National Commission has greatly enriched the country in various fields. Inclusive education is one of them. Among them, the Independent Commission for Education of India is the first to be mentioned. With the formulation of NEP 2020, the first education policy of the 21st century, it has evolved into a new paradigm for the Indian education system, revolutionizing it, especially in higher education. In an effort to make 'India a global knowledge superpower' and to implement major reforms in the education system of the country. The main aim and objective of this study is to make a comparative discussion between National Education Policy 1986 and India Inclusive Education Policy 2020. The sources of data include newspapers, NPE 1986 and NEP 2020 reports, government websites, various journals, etc. The major findings of the present study show that the procedures and teaching system of inclusive education have been changed in accordance with the earlier policies.

KEYWORDS: Education policy, National Education policy 1986, NEP 2020, Education, Inclusive Education. Drawbacks, Challenges.

INTRODUCTION

The main foundation of human civilization is its education system. Our country, India, is the birthplace of one of the oldest cultures in the world. Although the country suffered a little in the field of education under the rule of foreign rulers, the country has made great progress in the field of education through various commissions, committees and national education policies since independence. Among them National Education Commission 1986 and National Education Commission 2020 are very important. The Government of India recently replaced the old National Policy on Education (NPE) with a new policy which was formulated in 1986 and has been in effect for 34 years, with the New Education Policy of 2020 (NEP 2020). In 1986, the New National Policy of Education was implemented during Rajiv Gandhi's administration. This policy emphasized the importance of addressing disparities and ensuring

equal educational opportunities. It specifically targeted women, scheduled tribes, and scheduled castes, rather than focusing solely on children, integrated education. Key objectives of this policy included the expansion of scholarships, enhancement of senior education, and increased job recruitment for individuals from scheduled castes.

National Education policy (1968) and Inclusive Education

The definition of "inclusive education" is not used directly in the National Policy on Education (NPE) 1986 or 1968. However, it makes an effort to include inclusivity in the early stages of schooling in a number of ways. Emphasizing the previous policy's suggestions for special accommodations for special needs children, it has called for the implementation of a few new ones that either directly or indirectly

How to cite this paper: Umasankar Mandal "NPE 1986 and NEP 2020 on Inclusive Education in India a Comparative Study"

Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-9 | Issue-2, April 2025, pp.698-703, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd78493.pdf

IJTSRD78493

Copyright © 2025 by author (s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

support inclusive education. The National Education policy of 1986 underscores the necessity of addressing and eliminating all forms of educational disparities. It promotes the provision of educational opportunities that foster equality for women, Scheduled Castes, minorities, individuals with disabilities, and marginalized communities and regions. The policy particularly focuses on enhancing their educational access and suggests the establishment of support systems to facilitate their integration into the mainstream educational environment. It acknowledges the importance of catering to both physically and mentally challenged children, ensuring they receive equal consideration alongside their peers in the broader community. This strategy is designed to support their healthy development and empower them to approach life with optimism, resilience, and self-assurance.

The National Education policy (2020) and Inclusive Education

The National Education Policy (NEP 2020) has brought about significant changes in the Indian education system at all levels. It focuses on meeting the current national and global demand for education. The core objectives of the policy have been clearly articulated in its vision and are reflected in its various components. Each section and component emphasizes the importance of integrating all specific provisions to promote inclusion. The National Education Policy 2020 explicitly incorporates the concept of 'inclusive education' into the category of 'school education', thereby differentiating it from the previous two education policies. The vision articulated in the policy states that it aims to build an India-centric education system that plays a key role in transforming the country into a just and vibrant knowledge society by ensuring quality education for all. By focusing on 'Quality Education for All', the National Education Policy aspires to develop a cohesive education system that promotes equity, quality and complete education for children from diverse backgrounds. The principles embodied in this policy emphasize the need to respect diversity and to integrate local contexts into educational curricula and pedagogical methods, which are essential for achieving full equity and inclusion in education. It is expected that the inclusive measures proposed in the National Education Policy will contribute to the success of all students within the educational framework.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To know the recommendations regarding NPE 1986 in the field of inclusive education.
2. To find out the recommendations regarding inclusive education NEP 2020.

3. To compare NPE 1986 and NEP 2020 regarding inclusive education.

To find out the recommendations regarding inclusive education in NPE-1986.

Study Method:-

The content analysis method primarily qualitative in nature, has been utilized to enhance the comparative examination of NPE 1986 and NEP 2020 in relation to inclusive education.

Data Collection Methods:-

Data collection procedure involved primary sources, specifically the drafts of the National Policy on Education 1986 and the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, alongside secondary sources, which included websites, magazines, journals, newspapers, and digital content relevant to the analysis of inclusive education in the context of NPE 1986 and NEP 2020.

Findings of the study:-

The ensuing discussion focuses on the study's results, connecting them to the defined goals.

1. The recommendations regarding inclusive education in NPE 1986 to find out:-

- All teacher training programs will be restructured for the benefit of students. Emphasis will be placed on primary school teachers to specifically address the diverse issues experienced by children with disabilities.
- For the benefit of severely disabled children, special schools including hostels will be arranged at the district headquarters as far as possible so that their education is facilitated.
- Appropriate teacher training programs must be determined in advance to address the problems of children with special needs and disabilities.
- Skilled teacher training programs should be undertaken to address the various problems of children with special needs so that teachers can easily understand the subject.
- The Commission has observed that promoting equality requires not only providing equal opportunities for all but also developing favourable conditions to facilitate success.
- The 1986 policy emphasizes the elimination of all forms of discrimination, education for equality of women, education for Scheduled Castes, minorities, disabled and backward sections, education for different areas irrespective of religion, caste etc.
- To highlight the importance of physical and mental development for children with disabilities to the general public so that they are prepared for

normal development and are able to face life with hope, courage and confidence. And with an emphasis on social inclusion, it tries to deeply integrate this topic which will be very useful for later life.

Fig 1: Nep 1986 Major Importance On Inclusive Education.

2. The recommendations regarding inclusive education in NEP 2020:

- Establish free, suitable accommodation facilities on school premises to accommodate students who may have to travel long distances.
- In addition to ensuring access to good quality education, support women and transgender children to access education through various means, including appropriate provision of sanitation facilities, bicycles, conditional cash transfers, and other resources.
- Hostels will be arranged in the district headquarters for children with special needs, especially those with severe disabilities, to be admitted to special schools and accommodated as much as possible.
- The training programs for teachers, particularly aimed at elementary school instructors, will be revised to focus on the unique obstacles faced by children with disabilities.
- The establishment of NCC wings in secondary and higher secondary schools within tribal-dominated regions of various states will be supported to facilitate the development of students' natural talents and unique potential, emphasizing the importance of collaboration.
- Emphasizes equalizing educational opportunities and reducing disparities for students with special needs. Providing ways to meet the specific needs of students who have so far been denied equal opportunities in society.

Special Features of New Education Policy 2020

The NEP 2020 provides for universal access to education, covering all levels from schools to colleges and universities.

- The new policy, education framework has been changed to 5+3+3+4 years instead of the old Education Policy Framework of 10+2+3.
- It mentioned the establishment of a national mission and basic literacy program for comprehensive education of all the people of the country.
- Emphasis is being placed on promoting people of different languages and other Indian languages, taking into account the needs of all sections of people through education.
- Modifications to the assessment system have been established to improve the educational progress of students, such as formative and summative assessment, etc.
- A new national assessment center has been established in line with the modern era 'PARAKH'.
- Emphasis was placed on providing quality education in social and environmental sciences to all people of the country, regardless of religion, wealth, caste, or creed.
- Implementing transparency in the appointment of teachers based on merit, with an eye towards improving the education sector.
- This policy ensured that students had easy access to all learning resources, both offline and online.
- Authorities have been established to ensure that schools in the country and the state are built to maintain ideals and quality standards and adhere to those standards.
- Considering the future of the students, he has given special importance to introducing vocational education at the school and college levels for all students.
- Increase the total enrollment ratio of students in higher education to 50 percent.
- Therefore, introduce a multifaceted education system for students through a multifaceted education system.
- National Testing Agency and other central boards takes responsibility for conducting the tests for teacher eligibility in higher education.

- It was mentioned that all higher education councils and organizations should be brought under the same umbrella so that all sectors of the country's education system can be developed comprehensively and properly.
- The main goal of the National Education Policy 2020 is to achieve a gross enrollment ratio of 100 percent from pre-school to secondary levels by 2030, while the gross enrollment ratio in higher education, including vocational education and technical education, will be increased from 26.3 percent (2018) to 50 percent by 2035.

Fig 2: Nep 2020 Major Importance On Inclusive Education.

Similarities

- NPE 1986 and National Educational Policy 2020 It is proposed to eliminate discrimination and establish equal educational opportunities by focusing on the specific needs of all learners who have not yet experienced equality.
- Both policies emphasize the importance of including all students, regardless of their disabilities, in an inclusive educational environment. They emphasize the importance of using general school resources and access to community educational environments with appropriate support.
- Both policies emphasize the need to include Education for children with disabilities in teacher training programs so that trained teachers can easily address the problems of students with disabilities.
- Both policies have mentioned the provision of a solar system so that students can easily carry out their educational process, so that they do not face any obstacles in the educational process.

Dissimilarities

- The NEP 2020 was willing to pay more attention to gender equality issues, through the inclusion of transgender children and the Gender Inclusion Fund, which was not a focus in the NPE 1986, which only talked about inclusive education.
- The 1986 NPE emphasized the inclusion of all the deprived classes of students from the benefits. However, the NEP 2020 emphasizes social inclusion.
- The NEP 2020 seeks to remove ambiguity in allowing students to choose the school of their choice, Mentioning various neighborhood schools, special schools, and home-based education options to facilitate the education of children with disabilities, which were not considered in the NPE 1986.
- The 1986 NPE divided the goal of inclusive education into distinct categories of backward and isolated, marginalized communities and assigned separate categories for their challenges. But the NEP 2020 moves away from the traditional marginalization classification and, to some extent, recognizes the interconnectedness and multidimensionality of these exclusionary spaces.

CONCLUSION:

With this in mind, it can be said that the educational and administrative systems in our country have been working towards inclusive education for a long time in various ways in terms of policies and programs. Looking at the National Policy on Inclusive Education, we find that inclusive education has been proposed to be incorporated into the school culture, i.e., the culture, the educational system, and its curricula. The 1986 National Policy on Education (NPE) attempted to define the issue of inclusive education appropriately, but not specifically. Its conceptualization was based on issues of student access and equity, which later became the cornerstone of inclusive education. the 1986 NEP played a similar role by accepting and prioritizing the recommendations of the earlier policy (1986). The previous policy attempted to combine a number of aspects in order to keep inclusive education moderately vibrant and mainstreamed. However, the new National Education Policy 2020 gives full development to inclusive education. It truly recognizes the importance and necessity of inclusive education for the future growth of every child. It is not necessary to say that the country is making inclusive education contemporary, as seen in the new NEP 2020 towards national cohesion, social inclusion and national development. It is not necessary to say that the country is making inclusive education

contemporary, as seen in the new NEP 2020 towards national cohesion, social inclusion and national development.

References:

- [1] Document on National Policy on Education 1986: https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/npe.pdf5.Draft
- [2] Document on National Policy on Education 1986: https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/npe.pdf5.Draft
- [3] National Education Policy 2019: https://www.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Draft_NEP_2019_EN_Revised.pdf.
- [4] Education in India: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_India
- [5] National Education Policy 2019: https://www.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Draft_NEP_2019_EN_Revised.pdf.
- [6] NCERT (2007). Meeting Special Needs in Schools: A Manual. Accessed 10 November 2021. http://www.ncert.nic.in/html/pdf/inclusive_education/COVER.pdf
- [7] Singh, A. (21, March, 2005). Comprehensive Action Plan for Inclusive Education. New Delhi: Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India. Retrieved from <http://unicef.in>
- [8] UNESCO (2015). Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action for the implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 4. Accessed 20 April 2021. http://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/education-2030-incheon-framework-for-actionimplementation-of-sdg4-2016-en_2.pdf
- [9] Mayor, F. (1994). The Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education. World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality. Salamanca, Spain, 7-10 June 1994. UNESCO, Ministry of Education and Science, Spain. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org> .
- [10] UNESCO (1994).Salamanca Statement. Retrieved January 17, 2016 from United Nations Educational, Scientific, Cultural Organization.
- [11] Shah, R., Das, A. K., Desai, I. P. and Tiwari, A. (2014). Teachers' concerns about inclusive education in Ahmedabad, India. Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs.doi:10.1111/1471-3802.12054
- [12] Sanjeev. K. (2006).Inclusive Education: A Hope for Children with Special Needs. Available on <http://www.bihartimes.com>.
- [13] Ministry of Human Resource Development. National Policy on Education (PoA-1992). New Delhi: Government of India.
- [14] MHRD (2005).Action Plan for Inclusive Education of Children and Youth with Disabilities. Available on <http://www.education.nic.in>
- [15] Chatterjee, G. (2003). The global movement for inclusive education. Retrieved 11th January, 2016, from <http://www.indiatogether.org/2003/apr/edu-inclusive.htm>
- [16] Programme of Action (1992).National Policy on Education. Department of Education. New Delhi: Ministry of Human Resource Development Government of India.
- [17] Ottmar, E. R., Rimm-Kaufman, S. E., Larsen, R.A., & Berry, R. Q. (2015). Mathematical knowledge for teaching, standards-based mathematics teaching practices, and student achievement in the context of the responsive classroom approach. American Educational Research Journal, 52(4).
- [18] Moore, W. and Hammond, L. (2011). Using education assistants to help pave the road to literacy: Supporting oral language, letter-sound knowledge and phonemic awareness in the pre-primary year. Australian Journal of Learning Difficulties, 16(2), 85 – 110.
- [19] Collie, R. J., Shapka, J. D., & Perry, N. E.(2012). School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and efficacy. Journal of Educational Psychology, 104, 1189–1204.
- [20] Wolfendale, and Bastiani, J. (eds.) (2000). The contribution of parents to school effectiveness, London: David Fulton Publishers.
- [21] RCI. Integrated Education for Disabled Children 1974. Retrieved September 15, 2020, from <http://rehabcouncil.nic.in/>.

- [22] MHRD. National Education Policy 1986. Retrieved September 15, 2020 from <https://www.mhrd.gov.in/>.
- [23] NCBI. Mental Health Act 1987. Retrieved September 15, 2020 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.
- [24] MHRD. Programme of Action 1992. Retrieved September 15, 2020 from <https://www.mhrd.gov.in/>.
- [25] RCI. Rehabilitation Council of India Act 1992. Retrieved September 15, 2020, from <http://rehabcouncil.nic.in/>.
- [26] Balasundaram (2005). The Journey Towards Inclusive Education in India. Retrieved September 16, 2020, from <http://www.jlidd.jp/>.
- [27] NCBI. Rights of Person with Disability Act 2016. Retrieved September 15, 2020 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.
- [28] Narayan, John (2017). The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016: Does it address the needs of the persons with mental illness and their families. Indian J Psychiatry. (PMC free article).
- [29] Schuelka, Johnstone (2012). Global trends in meeting the educational rights of children with disabilities: from international institutions to local responses. Retrieved September 26, 2020, from <https://core.ac.uk/>.

